

Extended Data Figures for:

Flexibility of cell fates and functions across sex determination systems revealed by comparative single-cell analyses

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Extended Data Figure 1: The cell types of *T. scripta* gonads. a) UMAP projection after the integration of the six different samples colored by clusters calculated via Leiden. b) Stacked barplot with the cell type composition of each of the 6 different samples. Colors as in a). Note the similar compositions in Stg.15 samples and the sex-specific clusters in Stg. 23 samples (asterisks).

Extended Data Figure 4: Immunofluorescence localization and validation of single-cell markers. a-b). Representative immunofluorescence images of Stg.15 gonadal-mesonephros complex (a) and Stg. 16 gonads (b). DAPI in grey labels all cell nuclei, Gata4 in Cyan labels gonadal cells, Laminin in green elucidates morphological characteristics of early gonad (and mesonephros), Lhx9 in red labels pluripotent cells from in the coelomic epithelium. c) Representative images of cross sections of FPT and MPT gonads during sex determination stage. DAPI in grey labels all cell nuclei, Germ Cells are labeled in green with HuC/D and supporting cells in red with Sox9 (scalebar, 25 μ m).

Extended Data Figure 5: Expression of DEGs in the Supporting progenitors FPT vs MPT comparison. SCVI normalized expression per cluster and per sex of the 25 differentially expressed genes in the FPT vs MPT comparison among supporting progenitor cells.

Extended Data Figure 6: Twist1 expression in vertebrate gonads. a) Comparison of Twist1 and Sox9 expression at MPT and FPT at stgs.15,18 and 23 via Immunofluorescence. Twist1 is labeled in cyan, Sox9 in red, and HuC/D (labelling germ cells) in green. The gonad is outlined with white dashed line. Note the absence of Twist1+ cells at MPT (scalebar, 25 μ m) b) Immunofluorescence analysis of Twit1 and Sox9 expression in FPT gonadal sections throughout sex determination Immuno. Twist1 is labeled in cyan, Sox9 in red, and HuC/D

(labelling germ cells) in green. The gonad is outlined with white dashed line (scalebar, 25 μm). c) UMAP projection of SCVI integrated samples of chicken embryonic gonads from Estermann et al. 2020. d) UMAP projection of SCVI integrated samples of mouse embryonic gonads from Mayère et al. 2022. e-f) SCVI normalized expression of *Twist1* in chicken and mouse gonadal cell types.

Extended Data Figure 7: Functional enrichment in the Supporting progenitors FPT vs MPT comparison. Heatmap in which each row represents a GO BP term that is significantly enriched in either FPT (low NES values) or MPT (high NES values). Each column represents a gene. Terms are clustered according to their gene content. If a gene belongs to a particular term the cell will be colored black so that terms that contain similar genes can be appreciated.

Extended Data Figure 8: Expression of temperature response genes in *T. scripta* gonads. Dotplot displaying the expression of all the genes belonging to the GO Term *response to temperature*. They are grouped by the subterms *response to heat* or *response to cold*. The size of the dot represents the percentage of the cells expressing the gene in each cell type and the color the mean expression. b) Combined AUCCell scores of the gene set composed by the genes belonging to the GO terms in a) in each cell type at either FPT (F) or MPT (M). c) SCVI normalized expression of the genes encoding for the channels of the Trpv family in each cell type at FPT (F) or MPT (M).

Extended Data Figure 9: WGCNA modules calculated in the somatic gonad of chicken. a) Violin plot showing the distribution of Module Eigengene (ME) scores of the WGCNA modules in each of the cell types of the somatic gonad of chickens. b) Bar plots showing the membership (kME) of the top 20 genes more associated with each WGCNA module.

Extended Data Figure 10: Conservation of chicken WGCNA modules in *T. scripta*. Lollipop plots displaying network conservation FDR values between chicken and *T. scripta* of the different WGCNA modules calculated with NetRep. On the x-axis is represented the negative logarithm of the FDR of a permutation test assessing whether the module has a higher conservation metric than modules generated by chance. Density conservation metrics (top) assess whether the genes that are coexpressed in the WGCNA module in chicken are also coexpressed in *T. scripta*. **avg.weight**: average magnitude of edge weights. **avg.contrib**: average magnitude of the node contribution. **avg.cor**: average magnitude of the correlation coefficients. Connectivity preservation metrics (center) assess whether the hierarchy of the module is conserved, e.g the genes more central to the module in chicken are also central in *T. scripta*. **cor.degree**: concordance of the weighted degree. **cor.contrib**: concordance of the node contribution. **cor.cor**: concordance of the correlation structure. Other metrics like **coherence** measures the variance of the expression in *T. scripta* explained by the WGCNA module in chicken. **Summary** represents the average of all the other metrics. The size of the lollipop circle is proportional to the number of genes in the module.

Extended Data Figure 11: WGCNA modules calculated in the somatic gonad of *T. scripta*. a) Violin plot showing the distribution of Module Eigengene (ME) scores of the WGCNA modules in each of the cell types of the somatic gonad of *T. scripta*. b) Bar plots showing the membership (kME) of the top 20 genes more associated with each WGCNA module.

Extended Data Figure 12: Conservation of *T. scripta* WGCNA modules in chicken. a) Heatmap showing Module Eigengene (ME) scores of *T. scripta* WGCNA modules in each of the cell types of chicken. High ME scores imply that the genes of the *T. scripta* WGCNA module are active in the corresponding cell type of chicken. b) Lollipop plots displaying network conservation FDR values between *T. scripta* and chicken of the different WGCNA modules calculated with NetRep. On the x-axis is represented the negative logarithm of the FDR of a permutation test assessing whether the module has a higher conservation metric than modules generated by chance. See Extended Data Fig. 10. c) Scatterplot showing the membership (kME) of the genes belonging to the WGCNA module *Sertoli* calculated in *T. scripta* both in *T. scripta* (y-axis) and chicken (x-axis). Genes that are associated in *T. scripta* but not in chicken are labeled green (i.e. *Nkx3.1*). d-e) SCVI normalized expression of *Nkx3-1* in *T. scripta* and chicken gonadal cell types. f) As in c) but for the *T. scripta* module *Granulosa*. g-h) SCVI normalized expression of *Wnt16* in *T. scripta* and chicken gonadal cell types.

Extended Data Figure 13: WGCNA modules calculated in the somatic gonad of mouse. a) Violin plot showing the distribution of Module Eigengene (ME) scores of the WGCNA modules in each of the cell types of the somatic gonad of mouse. b) Bar plots showing the membership (kME) of the top 20 genes more associated with each WGCNA module.

Extended Data Figure 14: Conservation of mouse WGCNA modules in *T. scripta*. a) Heatmap showing Module Eigengene (ME) scores of mouse WGCNA modules in each of the *T. scripta* cell types. High ME scores imply that the genes of the chicken WGCNA module are active in the corresponding cell type of *T. scripta*. b) Lollipop plots displaying network conservation FDR values between chicken and *T. scripta* of the different WGCNA modules calculated with NetRep. On the x-axis is represented the negative logarithm of the FDR of a permutation test assessing whether the module has a higher conservation metric than modules generated by chance. See Extended Data Fig. 10. c) Scatterplot showing the membership (kME) of the genes belonging to the WGCNA module *Granulosa* calculated in mouse both in mouse (y-axis) and *T. scripta* (x-axis). Genes that are associated in mouse but not in *T. scripta* are labeled brown (i.e. *Irx3* and *Runx1*). d-e) SCVI normalized expression of *Irx3* in mouse and *T. scripta* gonadal cell types. f-g) SCVI normalized expression of *Runx1* in mouse and *T. scripta* gonadal cell types.

Extended Data Figure 16: Conservation of *T. scripta* WGCNA modules in mouse. a) Heatmap showing Module Eigengene (ME) scores of *T. scripta* WGCNA modules in each of the cell types of mouse. High ME scores imply that the genes of the *T. scripta* WGCNA module are active in the corresponding cell type of mouse. b) Lollipop plots displaying network conservation FDR values between *T. scripta* and mouse of the different WGCNA modules calculated with NetRep. On the x-axis is represented the negative logarithm of the FDR of a permutation test assessing whether the module has a higher conservation metric than modules generated by chance. See Extended Data Fig. 10. c) Scatterplot showing the membership (kME) of the genes belonging to the WGCNA module *Supporting I* calculated in *T. scripta* both in *T. scripta* (y-axis) and mouse (x-axis). Genes that are associated in *T. scripta* but not in chicken are labeled green (i.e. *Nkx3.1*). d) As in c) but for the *T. scripta* WGCNA module *Sertoli*. e) SCVI normalized expression of *Nkx3-1* in mouse gonadal cell types. f) As in c) but for the *T. scripta* module *Granulosa*. g-h) SCVI normalized expression of *Cyp19a1* in *T. scripta* and mouse gonadal cell types. i-j) SCVI normalized expression of *Ar* in *T. scripta* and mouse gonadal cell types.

Extended Data Figure 17: Steroidogenesis in *T. scripta* gonads. Representative immunofluorescence images of MPT and FPT gonadal cross sections at St.16. DAPI labels the nuclei in grey, HuC/D labels germ cells in green, Gata4 labels gonadal somatic cells in cyan, and Cyp11a1 labels steroidogenic cells in red. Note that Cyp11a1 labels the cytoplasm of Gata4+ cells located in the primitive cords at both temperatures (scalebar, 25 μm). White dashed line outlines the gonad.

Extended Data Figure 18: Trajectory analysis in *T. scripta* gonads. a-b) SCVI normalized expression of *Wnt4* and *Osr1*. c-d) UMAP embedding of FPT and MPT somatic gonads respectively, colored according to Leiden subclusters. The width of the connections between clusters represent the PAGA scores. Higher PAGA scores suggest a more likely transition between two cell types. e-f) Barplots represent the shortest distance in the PAGA graph between cell types present in early somatic gonads and terminal cell fates at either FPT or MPT respectively. Shortest distances imply a more likely transition.

a

b

Extended Data Fig. 19: Developmental origin of Sertoli and granulosa cells in chicken. a) PAGA trajectory analysis of female (ZW) somatic gonad cells. At the top left, UMAP embedding from a subcluster of female somatic cells displaying information of the stage at which they were sampled. At the top right, the same UMAP embedding but this time colored according to the Leiden subclusters. The width of the connections between clusters represent the PAGA scores. Higher PAGA scores suggest a more likely transition between two cell types. At the bottom, the barplots represent the shortest distance between early and terminal clusters. Shortest distances imply a more likely transition. b) As in a) but for male (ZZ) somatic gonad cells.

Extended Data Fig. 20: Developmental origin of Sertoli and granulosa cells in mice. a) PAGA trajectory analysis of female (XX) somatic gonad cells. At the top left, UMAP embedding from a subcluster of female somatic cells displaying information of the stage at which they were sampled. At the top right, the same UMAP

embedding but this time colored according to the Leiden subclusters. The width of the connections between clusters represent the PAGA scores. Higher PAGA scores suggest a more likely transition between two cell types. At the bottom, the barplots represent the shortest distance between early and terminal clusters. Shortest distances imply a more likely transition. b) As in b) but for male (XY) somatic gonad cells.

Extended Data Fig. 21: Dynamic expression along the Pax2+ mes. to granulosa differentiation trajectory.
 a) Diffusion component analysis of cells of the selected clusters in the Pax2+ mesenchyme to granulosa differentiation trajectory. Cells are colored either by cluster (left) or stage (right). b) Same diffusion component

reduction as in a) but now cells are colored according to the pseudotime in the differentiation trajectory to three different subclusters of Granulosa I cells. c) Heatmaps showing the scaled (left) and log10 normalized (right) expression of relevant genes along the different pseudotimes. The top heatmaps show the 50 top expressed transcription factors found to be dynamic in either of the three trajectories. The middle heatmaps focus on the expression of steroid hormone enzymes. The bottom heatmaps show a curated set of genes shown to be important for granulosa cell differentiation in mice (Bouma et al. 2010). At the bottom, a stacked barplot shows the proportion of cells of the different stages that are present in each pseudotime window. Darker colors represent later stages.

Extended Data Fig. 22: Dynamic expression along the Pax2+ to Sertoli cell differentiation trajectory. a) Diffusion component analysis of cells of the selected clusters in the Pax2+ mesenchyme to Sertoli cell differentiation trajectory. Cells are colored either by cluster (left) or stage (right). b) Same diffusion component

reduction as in a) but now cells are colored according to the pseudotime in the differentiation trajectory to either Sertoli I or Sertoli II cells. c) Heatmaps showing the scaled (left) and log10 normalized (right) expression of relevant genes along the different pseudotimes. The top heatmaps show the 50 top expressed transcription factors found to be dynamic in either of the two trajectories. The middle heatmaps focus on the expression of steroid hormone enzymes. The bottom heatmaps show a curated set of genes shown to be important for Sertoli cell differentiation in mice (Bouma et al. 2010). At the bottom, a stacked barplot shows the proportion of cells of the different stages that are present in each pseudotime window. Darker colors represent later stages.